

DIRECT AND INVERSE PROBLEMS FOR SUBSET SUMS WITH CERTAIN RESTRICTIONS

Himanshu Kumar Dwivedi¹

*Department of Mathematical Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology (BHU)
Varanasi, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India
himanshukrdwivedi.rs.mat21@itbhu.ac.in*

Raj Kumar Mistri²

*Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Technology Bhilai, Raipur, India
rkmistri@iitbhilai.ac.in*

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Abstract

Let A be a finite nonempty subset of an additive abelian group G . For a nonnegative integer α , let $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ denote the set of those elements of G which can be represented as a sum of a subset with at least α elements. Substituting $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$, we obtain the usual sets of subset sums. The direct problem for $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ is to find an optimal lower bound for the cardinality of $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ and the inverse problem is to characterize the sets A for which the cardinality of $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ is minimal. Recently, Balandraud studied the direct problem for the set of subsums $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ in the finite prime field \mathbb{F}_p , and Bhanja and Pandey proved some direct theorems for $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ for an arbitrary finite nonempty set A of integers. They also proved an inverse theorem for $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ in the case where the set A contains only nonnegative integers. We prove some inverse theorems for the set of subsums $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ for arbitrary finite nonempty sets of integers. The idea involved in the proofs also enables us to give new proofs of several direct theorems for $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ due to Bhanja and Pandey.

1. Introduction and Main Results

Let G be an additive abelian group. Given a subset B of a set $A \subseteq G$, let $\sigma(B)$ denote the subset sum of B which is the sum of all elements of the set B . Clearly, for the empty set ϕ , we have $\sigma(\phi) = 0$. Let $|S|$ denote the cardinality of the set S . Following the commonly used notation in zero-sum problems or sumsets problems (see [12]), the set of all subset sums of the set A is denoted by

$$\Sigma_0(A) = \{\sigma(B) : B \subseteq A\},$$

¹The work was done while the author was at IIT Bhilai.

²Corresponding author

and the set of all nontrivial subset sums of the set A is denoted by

$$\Sigma(A) = \{\sigma(B) : B \subseteq A \text{ and } |B| \geq 1\}.$$

For a fixed integer α such that $0 \leq \alpha \leq |A|$, if we consider only those subsets of the set A which have at least α elements, then the set of all subset sums of such subsets is denoted by

$$\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = \{\sigma(B) : B \subseteq A \text{ and } |B| \geq \alpha\}.$$

Obviously, we have $\Sigma_{\geq 0}(A) = \Sigma_0(A)$ and $\Sigma_{\geq 1}(A) = \Sigma(A)$.

The estimation of the optimal lower bound for the cardinality of the subset sums $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ is an important problem in additive combinatorics, called the direct problem. The problem of characterizing the sets for which the optimal lower bound is achieved for the cardinality of $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ is also an equally important problem, called the inverse problem. These are extremely important problems and have many applications related to the study of zero-sum constants such as Noether numbers, the Davenport constant, etc. (see [3, 4, 8, 12, 13, 17, 19, 20] and the references given therein).

Nathanson [17] proved the direct and inverse results for the sumset $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ in the case of $G = \mathbb{Z}$ and $\alpha = 1$. Balandraud studied the direct problems for $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ in the finite prime field \mathbb{F}_p for $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in [3], and for arbitrary α in [4]. Recently, Bhanja and Pandey [5, 6] proved the following direct theorems for $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ in the case of $G = \mathbb{Z}$ and arbitrary α .

Theorem 1 ([5, Theorem 2.1, Corollary 2.1]). *Let $k \geq 2$. Let α be an integer such that $1 \leq \alpha \leq k$. If A is a set of k nonnegative (nonpositive) integers and $0 \in A$, then*

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| \geq \frac{k(k-1)}{2} - \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)}{2} + 1. \tag{1}$$

If A is a set of k positive (negative) integers, then

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| \geq \frac{k(k+1)}{2} - \frac{\alpha(\alpha+1)}{2} + 1. \tag{2}$$

The lower bounds in Equation (1) and Equation (2) are best possible.

Theorem 2 ([6, Corollary 8]). *Let A be a finite set containing p positive integers, n negative integers and zero, where $1 \leq n \leq p$. For any integer $\alpha \in [1, n + p + 1]$, we have*

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| \geq \begin{cases} \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq \alpha \leq n \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n < \alpha \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p-1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n \leq p < \alpha. \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

The lower bound in Equation (3) is best possible.

Theorem 3 ([6, Theorem 7]). *Let A be a finite set containing p positive integers and n negative integers, where $1 \leq n \leq p$. For any integer $\alpha \in [1, n + p]$, we have*

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| \geq \begin{cases} \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq \alpha \leq n \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n < \alpha \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n \leq p < \alpha. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The lower bound in Equation (4) is best possible.

Remark 1. The lower bounds in Theorem 2 and Theorem 3 are obtained under the assumption that $n \leq p$. If $n > p$, then we can find the corresponding lower bound by replacing the set A by $-A = \{-a : a \in A\}$ and applying the above theorems.

For integers x and y , where $x \leq y$, we denote the interval of integers $\{n \in \mathbb{Z} : x \leq n \leq y\}$ by $[x, y]$. For a nonzero integer c and a set A , we write $c * A = \{ca : a \in A\}$. A k -term arithmetic progression in an additive abelian group G is a set of the form $\{a, a + d, \dots, a + (k - 1)d\}$ for some $a \in G$ and $0 \neq d \in G$.

In [5], the authors also proved the inverse theorems for $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ for arbitrary α in the case where the set A is a finite set of nonnegative integers including or excluding zero.

Theorem 4 ([5, Theorem 2.2, Corollary 2.3, Remark 2.1 and Remark 2.2]). *Let $k \geq 3$ be an integer, and let α be an integer such that $1 \leq \alpha \leq k - 2$. If A is a set of k nonnegative integers such that $0 \in A$ and*

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = \frac{k(k - 1)}{2} - \frac{\alpha(\alpha - 1)}{2} + 1,$$

then

$$A = d * [0, k - 1]$$

for some positive integer d except in the cases $k = 3$ and $k = 4$ when we have $A = \{0, a_1, a_2\}$ and $A = \{0, a_1, a_2, a_1 + a_2\}$, respectively, where $0 < a_1 < a_2$.

If A is a set of k positive integers such that

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = \frac{k(k + 1)}{2} - \frac{\alpha(\alpha + 1)}{2} + 1,$$

then

$$A = d * [1, k]$$

for some positive integer d except in the case $k = 3$ when we have $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_1 + a_2\}$, where $0 < a_1 < a_2$.

Remark 2. For $\alpha = k - 1$ and $\alpha = k$, we can find examples of sets A which are not arithmetic progressions but $|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)|$ are minimal (see [5, Remark 2.1 and Remark 2.2]).

In this paper, our objective is to prove the inverse theorems for $\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)$ for arbitrary finite sets of integers. We prove the following main results.

Theorem 5. *Let A be a finite set containing p positive integers, n negative integers and zero, where $1 \leq n \leq p$. Let $\alpha \in [1, n + p - 1]$, and let*

$$L = \begin{cases} \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq \alpha \leq n \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n < \alpha \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p-1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n \leq p < \alpha. \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Then

$$|\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)| = L$$

if and only if $A = d * [-n, p]$, where d is the smallest positive element of the set A .

Remark 3. For $\alpha = p + n$ and $\alpha = p + n + 1$, it can be easily seen that $|\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)|$ achieves the lower bound in Equation (5) for every set A containing p positive integers, n negative integers and zero.

Theorem 6. *Let A be a finite set containing p positive integers and n negative integers, where $1 \leq n \leq p$ and $n + p \geq 3$. Let $\alpha \in [1, n + p - 2]$ and*

$$L = \begin{cases} \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq \alpha \leq n \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n < \alpha \leq p; \\ \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n+1)}{2} + 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq n \leq p < \alpha. \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

Then

$$|\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)| = L$$

if and only if $A = d * \{-n, \dots, -1, 1, \dots, p\}$, where d is the smallest positive element of the set A .

Remark 4. For $\alpha = p + n - 1$ and $\alpha = p + n$, it can be easily seen that $|\Sigma_{\geq\alpha}(A)|$ achieves the lower bound in Equation (6) for every set A containing p positive integers and n negative integers with $n + p \geq 3$.

Remark 5. In Theorem 5 and Theorem 6, we have assumed that $n \leq p$. If $n > p$, then we can replace the set A by $-A = \{-a : a \in A\}$ and apply the above theorems to establish the corresponding inverse theorems.

We prove Theorem 5 and Theorem 6 in Subsection 2.2. In Subsection 2.1, we discuss some auxiliary results required for the proofs.

2. Proof of the Main Results

We begin with a definition.

Definition 1 (Generalized h -fold sumset [14]). Let G be an additive abelian group. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$ be a nonempty subset of G . Let $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{k-1})$ be an ordered k -tuple of positive integers, where r_i is the associated maximum repetitions of $a_i \in A$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$. For a positive integer h , we define the generalized h -fold sumset

$$h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A = \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} s_i a_i : s_i \in \mathbb{Z}, 0 \leq s_i \leq r_i \text{ for } i = 0, 1, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} s_i = h \right\}.$$

Note that whenever we write $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$, we assume that given the ordered k -tuple $\bar{\mathbf{r}}$, the elements of the set A are in a fixed order. If $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r, \dots, r)$, we simply write $h^{(r)}A$ in place of $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$. For $r = h$ and $r = 1$, we get the usual h -fold sumset hA and the restricted h -fold sumset $h \hat{A}$, respectively. These particular sumsets have been studied extensively in literatures (see [1, 2, 7, 9, 10, 11, 18, 21] and the references given therein). The direct and inverse problems for the unified sumset $h^{(r)}A$ have been studied by Mistri and Pandey [14] in \mathbb{Z} , and by Monopoli [16] in \mathbb{Z}_p , where p is a prime number (see [15] also). Yang and Chen [22] have studied the direct and inverse problems for the sumset $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$ in \mathbb{Z} .

2.1. Idea of the Proof and Auxiliary Results

The main idea of the proof is to express the set of subset sums $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ as a generalized h -fold sumset $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A'$ for some specific values of h , $\bar{\mathbf{r}}$ and a specific set A' (see Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 below) and apply the inverse results for the generalized h -fold sumset in \mathbb{Z} . We remark that this approach also enables us to give new proofs of the existing direct and inverse theorems for the sumset $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ (see Subsection 2.2 and Subsection 2.3).

It is easy to see that $\Sigma_{\geq 0}(A) = \Sigma(A) = \Sigma_{\geq 1}(A)$ if $0 \in \Sigma_{\geq 1}(A)$, and $\Sigma_{\geq 0}(A) = \Sigma_{\geq 1}(A) \cup \{0\}$ if $0 \notin \Sigma_{\geq 1}(A)$. Therefore, we consider only the positive values of α . Whenever we say that A is an ordered set, we mean that the elements of the set A are kept in a fixed order. A simple set-theoretic argument yields the following results.

Lemma 1. *Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$ be an ordered finite nonempty subset of an additive abelian group G with $a_0 = 0$, where k is a positive integer. Let α be an integer such that $1 \leq \alpha \leq k$ and let $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (k - \alpha + 1, \underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{k-1 \text{ times}})$. Then $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = k^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$.*

Lemma 2. *Let k and α be integers such that $1 \leq \alpha \leq k$. Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\}$ be an ordered finite nonempty subset of an additive abelian group G with $0 \notin A$.*

Consider the ordered set $A_0 = \{a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\} \subseteq G$, where $a_0 = 0$. Let $\bar{r} = (k - \alpha, \underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{k \text{ times}})$. Then $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = k^{(\bar{r})}A_0$.

The following results for the generalized h -fold sumset will also be crucial for the proofs. To state the results, we need to fix some notation which will be used throughout the paper. If x and y are integers such that $x > y$, then we take $\sum_{j=x}^y f(j) = 0$, where f is a function. Given positive integers h and k , and an ordered k -tuple $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{k-1})$ of positive integers, define

$$L(\bar{r}, h) = \left(\sum_{j=\eta+1}^{k-1} jr_j - \sum_{j=0}^{\mu-1} jr_j \right) + \eta\theta - \mu\delta + 1,$$

where $\mu = \mu(\bar{r}, h)$ is the largest integer and $\eta = \eta(\bar{r}, h)$ is the least integer such that

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\mu-1} r_j \leq h, \quad \sum_{j=\eta+1}^{k-1} r_j \leq h$$

and

$$\delta = \delta(\bar{r}, h) = h - \sum_{j=0}^{\mu-1} r_j, \quad \theta = \theta(\bar{r}, h) = h - \sum_{j=\eta+1}^{k-1} r_j.$$

These definitions of $\mu = \mu(\bar{r}, h)$, $\eta = \eta(\bar{r}, h)$ and $L(\bar{r}, h)$ will be used throughout the paper.

Theorem 7 ([22, Theorem 1]). *Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$ be a set of integers with $a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{k-1}$, where k is a positive integer. Let $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{k-1})$ be an ordered k -tuple of positive integers, and h be an integer satisfying $2 \leq h \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} r_j$.*

Then

$$|h^{(\bar{r})}A| \geq L(\bar{r}, h).$$

This lower bound is best possible.

Theorem 8 ([22, Theorem 2]). *Let $k \geq 5$ be an integer. Let $\bar{r} = (r_0, \dots, r_{k-1})$ be an ordered k -tuple of positive integers and h be an integer satisfying*

$$2 \leq h \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} r_j - 2.$$

If A is a set of k integers, then

$$|h^{(\bar{r})}A| = L(\bar{r}, h)$$

if and only if A is a k -term arithmetic progression.

Theorem 9 ([22, Theorem 3]). *Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, a_2\}$ be a set of integers with $a_0 < a_1 < a_2$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r_0, r_1, r_2)$ be an ordered 3-tuple of positive integers. Suppose that h is an integer with $2 \leq h \leq r_0 + r_1 + r_2 - 2$. Then*

- (i) *for $r_1 = 1$, we have $|h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A| = L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, h)$;*
- (ii) *for $r_1 \geq 2$, we have $|h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A| = L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, h)$ if and only if A is a 3-term arithmetic progression.*

Theorem 10 ([22, Theorem 4]). *Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3\}$ be a set of integers with $a_0 < a_1 < a_2 < a_3$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r_0, r_1, r_2, r_3)$ be an ordered 4-tuple of positive integers. Suppose that h is an integer with $2 \leq h \leq r_0 + r_1 + r_2 + r_3 - 2$. Then*

- (i) *for $r_1 = r_2 = 1$, we have $|h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A| = L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, h)$ if and only if $a_1 - a_0 = a_3 - a_2$;*
- (ii) *for $r_1 \geq 2$ or $r_2 \geq 2$, we have $|h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A| = L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, h)$ if and only if A is a 4-term arithmetic progression.*

Remark 6. When using the sumset $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$, the relative orders of elements listed in the set A are considered. Therefore, from now onwards, whenever we use the sumset $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$ or $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A_0$ in a proof, we write the elements of the sets A and A_0 in a fixed order.

Let $\pi : [1, k] \rightarrow [1, k]$ be a permutation, where k is a positive integer. For an ordered set $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\}$ and an ordered k -tuple $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k)$ of positive integers, denote the ordered set $A_\pi = \{a_{\pi(1)}, a_{\pi(2)}, \dots, a_{\pi(k)}\}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_\pi = (r_{\pi(1)}, r_{\pi(2)}, \dots, r_{\pi(k)})$. Since the order of the elements in the set A is assumed to be fixed in the definition of $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$, the following lemma will be useful in expressing the generalized h -fold sumset $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$ as a similar generalized h -fold sumset, if we change the order of the elements in the set A .

Lemma 3. *Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\}$ be an ordered finite nonempty subset of an additive abelian group G , where k is a positive integer. Let $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k)$ be an ordered k -tuple of positive integers. Let $h \geq 2$ be an integer and let π be a permutation of $[1, k]$. Then*

$$h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A = h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}}_\pi)}A_\pi.$$

Proof. The proof is easy, and is left to the reader. □

2.2. Proof of Theorem 5 and Theorem 6

Proof of Theorem 5. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, a_n, a_{n+1}, \dots, a_{n+p}\}$, where $a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_n = 0 < a_{n+1} < \dots < a_{n+p}$. Then $k = |A| = p + n + 1$. Let

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1}, r_n, r_{n+1}, \dots, r_{n+p}),$$

where $r_0 = r_1 = \dots = r_{n-1} = r_{n+1} = \dots = r_{n+p} = 1$ and $r_n = k - \alpha + 1$. It follows from Lemma 1 and Lemma 3 that $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = k^{(\bar{r})}A$. We can verify that $L = L(\bar{r}, k)$. If $k = 3$, then clearly, $p = n = 1$. Hence $A = \{a_0, a_1, a_2\}$ with $a_0 < 0 = a_1 < a_2$ and $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, r_2) = (1, k - \alpha + 1, 1)$. Since $r_1 = k - \alpha + 1 \geq 3 > 2$, it follows from Theorem 9 that $|k^{(\bar{r})}A| = |\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L = L(\bar{r}, k)$ if and only if A is an arithmetic progression. Hence

$$a_1 - a_0 = a_2 - a_1$$

which implies $a_0 = -a_2$, and so $A = \{-a_2, 0, a_2\} = a_2 * [-1, 1]$.

If $k = 4$, then clearly we have $n = 1$ and $p = 2$. Hence $A = \{a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3\}$ with $a_0 < 0 = a_1 < a_2 < a_3$ and $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, r_2, r_3) = (1, k - \alpha + 1, 1, 1)$. Since $r_1 = k - \alpha + 1 \geq 3 > 2$, it follows from Theorem 10 that $|k^{(\bar{r})}A| = |\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L = L(\bar{r}, k)$ if and only if A is an arithmetic progression. Hence

$$a_1 - a_0 = a_2 - a_1 = a_3 - a_2$$

which implies $a_0 = -a_2$ and $a_3 = 2a_2$, and so $A = \{-a_2, 0, a_2, 2a_2\} = a_2 * [-1, 2]$.

If $k \geq 5$, then it follows from Theorem 8 that $|k^{(\bar{r})}A| = |\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L = L(\bar{r}, k)$ if and only if A is an arithmetic progression. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 - a_0 = a_2 - a_1 = \dots = a_{n-1} - a_{n-2} = a_n - a_{n-1} \\ = a_{n+1} - a_n = a_{n+2} - a_{n+1} = \dots = a_{n+p} - a_{n+p-1}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies $a_{n-j} = -ja_{n+1}$ for $j = 1, \dots, n$ and $a_{n+j} = ja_{n+1}$ for $j = 2, \dots, p$, and so $A = a_{n+1} * [-n, p]$. Thus in all cases, we have $|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L(\bar{r}, h)$ if and only if $A = a_{n+1} * [-n, p]$. This completes the proof. \square

Proof of Theorem 6. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, a_{n+1}, \dots, a_{n+p}\}$ and $A_0 = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, a_n, a_{n+1}, \dots, a_{n+p}\}$ with $a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{n-1} < 0 = a_n < a_{n+1} < \dots < a_{n+p}$. Let $k = |A| = p+n$, $k_0 = |A_0| = p+n+1$, and let $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1}, r_n, r_{n+1}, \dots, r_{n+p})$, where $r_0 = r_1 = \dots = r_{n-1} = r_{n+1} = \dots = r_{n+p} = 1$ and $r_n = k - \alpha$. Then by Lemma 2 and Lemma 3, we have $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = k^{(\bar{r})}A_0$. Therefore, $|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = |k^{(\bar{r})}A_0|$. We can verify that $L = L(\bar{r}, k)$.

If $k = 3$, then clearly we have $n = 1$ and $p = 2$. Hence $A = \{a_0, a_2, a_3\}$ and $A_0 = \{a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3\}$ with $a_0 < 0 = a_1 < a_2 < a_3$ and $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, r_2, r_3) = (1, k - \alpha, 1, 1)$. Since $r_1 = k - \alpha \geq 2$, it follows from Theorem 10 that $|k^{(\bar{r})}A_0| = |\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L = L(\bar{r}, k)$ if and only if A_0 is an arithmetic progression. Hence

$$a_1 - a_0 = a_2 - a_1 = a_3 - a_2$$

which implies $a_0 = -a_2$ and $a_3 = 2a_2$, and so $A_0 = \{-a_2, 0, a_2, 2a_2\}$. Hence $A = \{-a_2, a_2, 2a_2\} = a_2 * \{-1, 1, 2\}$.

If $k \geq 4$, then it follows from Theorem 8 that $|k^{(\bar{r})}A_0| = |\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L = L(\bar{r}, k)$ if and only if A_0 is an arithmetic progression. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 - a_0 &= a_2 - a_1 = \cdots = a_{n-1} - a_{n-2} = a_n - a_{n-1} \\ &= a_{n+1} - a_n = a_{n+2} - a_{n+1} = \cdots = a_{n+p} - a_{n+p-1} \end{aligned}$$

which implies $a_{n-j} = -ja_{n+1}$ for $j = 1, \dots, n$ and $a_{n+j} = ja_{n+1}$ for $j = 2, \dots, p$, and so $A_0 = a_{n+1} * [-n, p]$. Therefore, $A = a_{n+1} * \{-n, -(n-1), \dots, -1, 1, 2, \dots, p\}$.

Thus in all cases, we have $|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = L$ if and only if

$$A = d * \{-n, -(n-1), \dots, -1, 1, 2, \dots, p\},$$

where d is the smallest element of the set A . This completes the proof. □

Remark 7. Theorem 4 also can be proved by a similar approach. We omit the details.

2.3. New Proofs of Direct Theorems

The idea used to prove Theorem 5 and Theorem 6 also enables us to give new proofs of the direct theorems for $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$. Here we give proofs of Theorem 1 and Theorem 2. The proof of Theorem 3 is similar to the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 1. First assume that A is a set of $k \geq 2$ nonnegative integers with $0 \in A$. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$, where $0 = a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{k-1}$. If $\alpha = k$, then $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = \{a_0 + a_1 + \dots + a_{k-1}\}$, and thus the theorem holds in this case. Therefore, we can assume that $1 \leq \alpha \leq k-1$. Let $h = k$, and $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{k-1})$, where $r_0 = k - \alpha + 1$ and $r_1 = r_2 = \dots = r_{k-1} = 1$. It follows from Lemma 1 that $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = h^{(\bar{r})}A$.

Clearly, the integers h, k and k -tuple \bar{r} satisfy the assumptions of Theorem 7. It is easy to see that $\mu = \alpha$ and $\eta = 0$. Therefore, $\delta = h - \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} 1 = k - \alpha = 0$ and $\theta = h - \sum_{j=\eta+1}^{k-1} 1 = k - (k-1) = 1$. Hence

$$L(\bar{r}, h) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} j - \sum_{j=1}^{\alpha-1} j \right) + 1 = \frac{k(k-1)}{2} - \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)}{2} + 1.$$

Therefore, it follows from Theorem 7 that

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = |h^{(\bar{r})}A| \geq L(\bar{r}, h) = \frac{k(k-1)}{2} - \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)}{2} + 1.$$

We can see that the lower bound in Equation (1) is best possible by taking the set $A = [0, k-1]$, where $k \geq 2$. This proves the first part of the theorem.

A similar argument proves the theorem in the case where the set A is a set of $k \geq 2$ positive integers. □

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $A = \{-b_n, -b_{n-1}, \dots, -b_1, 0, a_1, \dots, a_p\}$, where

$$-b_n < -b_{n-1} < \dots < -b_1 < 0 < a_1 < \dots < a_p.$$

Let $k = |A| = p + n + 1$ and $\bar{r} = (r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1}, r_n, r_{n+1}, \dots, r_{n+p})$, where $r_0 = r_1 = \dots = r_{n-1} = r_{n+1} = \dots = r_{n+p} = 1$ and $r_n = k - \alpha + 1$. Then by Lemma 1 and Lemma 3, we have $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A) = k^{(\bar{r})}A$. Therefore, $|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = |k^{(\bar{r})}A| \geq L(\bar{r}, k)$.

Case 1 ($1 \leq \alpha \leq n \leq p$). In this case, we can easily determine that $\mu = \eta = n, \delta = p + 1$ and $\theta = n + 1$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} L(\bar{r}, k) &= \left(\sum_{j=n+1}^{p+n} jr_j - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} jr_j \right) + n(n+1) - n(p+1) + 1 \\ &= \left(\sum_{j=n+1}^{p+n} j - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j \right) + n^2 - pn + 1 \\ &= \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2 ($1 \leq n < \alpha \leq p$). In this case, we can determine that $\mu = \alpha, \eta = n, \delta = 0$ and $\theta = n + 1$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} L(\bar{r}, k) &= \left(\sum_{j=n+1}^{p+n} jr_j - \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} jr_j \right) + n(n+1) - 0 + 1 \\ &= \left(\sum_{j=n+1}^{p+n} j - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j - n(k - \alpha + 1) - \sum_{j=n+1}^{\alpha-1} j \right) + n^2 + n + 1 \\ &= \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Case 3 ($1 \leq n \leq p < \alpha \leq p+n$). Write $\alpha = p+x$. Then $1 \leq x \leq n$. By considering the subcases $x = 1$ and $2 \leq x \leq n$, we can see that in both the subcases, we have

$\mu = \alpha = p + x, \eta = n - x, \delta = 0$ and $\theta = 0$. Hence for $x = 1$, we have $\alpha = p + 1$ and

$$\begin{aligned} L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, k) &= \left(\sum_{j=n}^{p+n} jr_j - \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} jr_j \right) + 0 - 0 + 1 \\ &= n(k - \alpha + 1) + \sum_{j=n+1}^{p+n} j - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j - n(k - \alpha + 1) - \sum_{j=n+1}^{\alpha-1} j + 1 \\ &= \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1. \\ &= \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p-1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Now for $2 \leq x \leq n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, k) &= \left(\sum_{j=n-x+1}^{p+n} jr_j - \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} jr_j \right) + 0 - 0 + 1 \\ &= \left(\sum_{j=n-x+1}^{n-1} j + n(k - \alpha + 1) + \sum_{j=n+1}^{p+n} j \right) \\ &\quad - \left(\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j + n(k - \alpha + 1) - \sum_{j=n+1}^{\alpha-1} j \right) + 1 \\ &= \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p-1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Thus in both the subcases, we have

$$L(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, k) = \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p-1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1.$$

Case 4 ($\alpha = p + n + 1$). In this case, clearly we have

$$|\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)| = 1 = \frac{p(p+1)}{2} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-p)(\alpha-p-1)}{2} - \frac{(\alpha-n)(\alpha-n-1)}{2} + 1.$$

Combining all the cases, we get the desired lower bound in Equation (3). We can see that the lower bound in Equation (3) is best possible by taking the set $A = [-n, p]$. This completes the proof. \square

3. Concluding Remarks

We have shown the connection between the set of subsums $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ and the generalized h -fold sumset $h^{(\bar{\mathbf{r}})}A$ in an additive abelian group G . Thus the problem

of studying the set of subsums $\Sigma_{\geq \alpha}(A)$ in arbitrary abelian groups reduces to the study of the generalized h -fold sumset $h^{(\bar{r})}A$. Therefore, it would be an important and interesting problem to investigate this sumset in general abelian groups.

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